

Symbols, names, and units used for Henry's law constants in the literature

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Miscellaneous definitions, symbols, names and units have been used for Henry's law constants in the literature. A survey is shown in this document. It contains about 700 publications taken from the compilation of Sander (2015) plus a couple of papers about non-aqueous solutions. The list has been prepared by the IUPAC Task Group "Henry's law constants" (<https://iupac.org/project/2019-025-1-100>). Its aim is to provide an overview what terminology is used in the literature. There is no claim to completeness. For simplicity, upright and italics fonts are not differentiated when quoting symbols from other publications. If the symbol contains a subscript referring to a species (e.g., H_{O_3} , H_x , H_1 , H_i), these are not included. If the papers use several names or symbols, it may be that not all are shown in this survey.

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Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
Henry's law solubility constants H_s (used in 263 publications)				
concentration/pressure H_s^{cp} (used in 155 publications)				
		M/atm		Swain and Thornton (1962)
		M/atm		Bagno et al. (1991)
		M/atm		Dong and Dasgupta (1986)
		M/mmHg		Marti et al. (1997)
		M/mmHg		Westheimer and Ingraham (1956)
		M/mmHg		Guthrie (1973)
		M/Pa		Li et al. (1998)
	distribution coefficient	M/atm		Lovelock et al. (1972)
	gas solubility	M/atm		Mozurkewich (1995)
	Henry coefficient	M/atm		Mentel et al. (2004)
	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Petersen et al. (1998)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lee and Zhou (1994)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Jaeglé et al. (1996)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kroll et al. (2005)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Roberts et al. (2008)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Holdren et al. (1984)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Fried et al. (1994)
	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Aprea et al. (2007)
	Henry's law solubility	M/atm		Disselkamp et al. (1999)
A	solubility	M/atm		Manogue and Pigford (1960)
c/p	activity coefficient	M/mmHg		Hine and Weimar (1965)
E	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lelieveld and Crutzen (1991)
H		M/atm		Schwartz and White (1981)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Iraci et al. (1999)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Treves et al. (2000)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Heal et al. (1995)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Cheung et al. (2000)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Harrison et al. (2002)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Müller and Heal (2001)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Barcellos da Rosa et al. (2003)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Hanson and Ravishankara (1991)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Weinstein-Lloyd and Schwartz (1991)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Schwartz (1984)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Hanson et al. (1992)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Servant et al. (1991)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Seinfeld (1986)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Kames and Schurath (1992)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Rudich et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Park and Lee (1988)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Lee and Schwartz (1981)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Villalta et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Pandis and Seinfeld (1989)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Schwartz (1986)
H	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm	also: Henry's law solubility	De Bruyn et al. (1995a)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Bartlett and Margerum (1999)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Scheer et al. (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		George et al. (1994a)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		George et al. (1994b)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lin and Pehkonen (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Katrib et al. (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Leriche et al. (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Mozurkewich (1986)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Pollien et al. (2003)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Miller and Stuart (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Katrib et al. (2003)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Sander et al. (2006)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Feigenbrugel et al. (2004b)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Gershenson et al. (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Sander et al. (2011)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kutsuna et al. (2005)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kutsuna et al. (2004)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Roberts et al. (2011)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Chen et al. (2003)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Reyes-Pérez et al. (2008)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Allou et al. (2011)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Poulain et al. (2010)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Shi et al. (1999)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Chan et al. (2010)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		De Bruyn et al. (1994)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Vogt et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Betterton and Hoffmann (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kanakidou et al. (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kames et al. (1991)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Luke et al. (1989)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Behnke et al. (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Shepson et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kames and Schurath (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Amels et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Mirabel et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Gaffney et al. (1987)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Brian et al. (1962)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lindinger et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Régimbal and Mozurkewich (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Zhou and Lee (1992)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Graedel and Goldberg (1983)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Frenzel et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Schwarzenbach et al. (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Seyfioglu and Odabasi (2007)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Betterton (1991)
H	Henry's law constant	M/atm	also: Henry's law solubility	Lee and Zhou (1993)
H	solubility coefficient	M/atm		Kramers et al. (1961)
H, K_H, H'	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Benkelberg et al. (1995)
H, K_{PC}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Karl et al. (2003)
H_x	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Strekowski and George (2005)
H_{cc}, H_{cp}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lee et al. (2013)
K	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Martin and Damschen (1981)
k	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Yoshizumi et al. (1984)
K	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Hedgecock et al. (2005)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
K	partition coefficient	M/atm		Zhou and Mopper (1990)
K	solubility	M/atm		Boggs and Buck (1958)
K'	partial pressure equilibrium constant	M/atm		Warner and Weiss (1985)
$K(\text{h})$	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lind and Kok (1994)
k_{H}°	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Krysztofiak et al. (2012)
K_{H}°	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Brimblecombe (1986)
K_0	solubility coefficient	M/atm		Weiss (1974)
K_0	solubility coefficient	M/atm		Weiss and Price (1980)
K_{H}	Henry coefficient	M/atm		Thomas et al. (1998)
k_{H}	Henry constant	M/atm		Sauer (1997)
k_{H}	Henry constant	M/atm		Keßel (2011)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Warneck (1999)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Warneck (2006)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Warneck (2007)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Betterton and Robinson (1997)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Warneck and Williams (2012)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Kish et al. (2013)
K_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Johnson et al. (1996)
k_{H}	Henry's law coefficient	M/bar		Warneck (2003)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Shon et al. (2005)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Hoffmann and Calvert (1985)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Iliuta and Larachi (2005)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Iverfeldt and Lindqvist (1982)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Ip et al. (2009)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kutsuna and Horia (2008)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kutsuna and Hori (2008)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Huang and Chen (2010)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Li et al. (2004)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kutsuna (2013)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Leng et al. (2013)
k_{h}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Compernelle and Müller (2014a)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Kim and Kim (2014)
k_{h}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Compernelle and Müller (2014b)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Hough (1991)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Jacob (1986)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Dasgupta and Dong (1986)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Hwang and Dasgupta (1985)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Möller and Mauersberger (1992)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Keene and Galloway (1986)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Betterton (1992)
K_{h}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		O'Sullivan et al. (1996)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Keene et al. (1995)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Martin (1984)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Jacob et al. (1989)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Maahs (1982)
K_{H}	Henry's law constant	M/atm	also: gas-liquid partition coefficient	Warneck (2005)
K_{S}	solubility constant	M/atm		Chameides (1986)
K_{S}	solubility constant	M/atm		Chameides (1984)
$K_{(\text{aq})}$		M/atm		Hoffmann and Jacob (1984)
K_{AW}	air-water equilibrium constant	M/atm		Saxena and Hildemann (1996)
m/p		M/mmHg		Bohon and Claussen (1951)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
HL	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Staffelbach and Kok (1993)
HLC	Henry's law constant	M/atm		von Hartungen et al. (2004)
HLC	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Gautier et al. (2003)
HLC	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Feigenbrugel et al. (2004a)
HLC	Henry's law constant	mol/(m ³ Pa)		Li et al. (2008)
HLC, K_{PC}	Henry's law constant	M/atm		Schuhfried et al. (2011)
concentration/concentration H_g^{cc} (used in 63 publications)				
		1		Burkhard and Guth (1981)
	distribution ratio	1		Tsibul'skii et al. (1979)
	partition coefficient	1		Munson et al. (1964)
	partition coefficient	1		Stoelting and Longshore (1972)
	partition coefficient	1		Pearson and McConnell (1975)
γ	activity coefficient	1		Hine and Mookerjee (1975)
γ_S	Ostwald absorption coefficient	1		Ben-Naim and Wilf (1980)
κ	distribution coefficient	1		Komiyama and Inoue (1980)
λ	liquid/air partition coefficient	1		Johanson and Dynésius (1988)
λ	Ostwald solubility coefficient	1		Steward et al. (1973)
λ	Ostwald solubility coefficient	1		Edelist et al. (1964)
λ	partition coefficient	1		Lerman et al. (1983)
λ	partition coefficient	1		Falk et al. (1990)
λ_A	partition coefficient	1		Sato and Nakajima (1979a)
H	gas-liquid absorption equilibrium constant	1		Komiyama and Inoue (1978)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Scharlin and Battino (1994)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Abraham et al. (2007)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Terraglio and Manganeli (1967)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Hales and Drewes (1979)
H	solubility constant	1		Andrew and Hanson (1961)
H_A	Henry's law coefficient	1		Snider and Dawson (1985)
K		1		Eguchi et al. (1973)
k	distribution coefficient	1		Hellmann (1987)
K	distribution ratio	1		Vitenberg and Dobryakov (2008)
K	gas-liquid partition coefficient	1		Rohrschneider (1973)
K	gas-liquid partition coefficient	1		Etre et al. (1993)
K	gas-to-water partition coefficient	1		Li et al. (1993)
K	gas/liquid partition coefficient	1		Park et al. (1987)
K	Henry's law constant	1		Wen and Muccitelli (1979)
K	liquid/gas partition coefficient	1		Guitart et al. (1989)
K	partition coefficient	1		Vitenberg et al. (1974)
K	partition coefficient	1		Schwarz and Wasik (1977)
K	partition coefficient	1		Bakierowska and Trzeczynski (2003)
K	partition coefficient	1		Brown and Wasik (1974)
K	partition coefficient	1		Burnett (1963)
K	partition coefficient	1		Vitenberg et al. (1975)
K	partition coefficient	1		Wasik and Tsang (1970)
K	partition coefficient	1		Kolb et al. (1992)
K	vapor-liquid equilibrium distribution coefficient	1		Kieckbusch and King (1979)
$K(w/v)$	Henry's constant	1		Leistra (1970)
k^0	zero pressure partition coefficient	1		Cooling et al. (1992)
k^0	zero pressure partition coefficient	1		Khalfouli and Newsham (1994a)
K_{AW}^c	air-water partition coefficient	1		Lei et al. (2007)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
K_{AW}	air/water partition coefficient	1		Jönsson et al. (1982)
K_h	Henry's law constant	1		Marsh and McElroy (1985)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1		Battino et al. (1983)
K_L	partition coefficient	1		Hartkopf and Karger (1973)
$K_{V \rightarrow W}$	water-to-vapor distribution coefficient	1		Gibbs et al. (1991)
$K_{W/A}$	partition coefficient	1		Zhang et al. (2002)
K_{WA}	water-air partition coefficient	1		Hoff et al. (1993)
K_W	gas-to-water partition coefficient	1		Abraham and Acree (2007)
K_W	gas-water partition coefficient	1		Li and Carr (1993)
K_W	partition coefficient	1		Abraham et al. (2008)
K_W	partition coefficient	1		Caron et al. (1985)
L	distribution number	1		Fredenhagen and Liebster (1932)
L	distribution number	1		Fredenhagen and Wellmann (1932a)
L	distribution number	1		Fredenhagen and Wellmann (1932b)
L	Ostwald coefficient	1		Clever et al. (2005)
L^W	Ostwald solubility coefficient	1		Abraham et al. (1994)
L_c	Ostwald concentration coefficient	1		Bebahani et al. (2002)
L_W	Ostwald solubility coefficient	1		Abraham et al. (1990)
W	partition coefficient	1		Sato and Nakajima (1979b)
LWAPC	water-to-air partition coefficient	1		Meylan and Howard (1991)

molality/pressure H_s^{bp} (used in 22 publications)

		mol/(kg 10 ⁵ Pa)	unit results from standard states	
		mol/(kg atm)		Wagman et al. (1982)
		mol/(kg atm)		Barrett et al. (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Johnstone and Leppla (1934)
H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Leu and Zhang (1999)
K'	partial pressure equilibrium constant	mol/(kg atm)		Bu and Warner (1995)
K'	solubility coefficient	mol/(kg atm)		Bullister et al. (2002)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Khan et al. (1992)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Khan et al. (1995)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Bowden et al. (1998a)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Bowden et al. (1998b)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Huthwelker et al. (1995)
K_H	Henry's law coefficient	mol/(kg atm)		Kampf et al. (2013)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Clegg et al. (1996)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Guo and Brimblecombe (2007)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Clegg and Brimblecombe (1989)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Watts and Brimblecombe (1987)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg bar)		Becker et al. (1998)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg bar)		Becker et al. (1996)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Khan and Brimblecombe (1992)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Brimblecombe et al. (1992)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg atm)		Bowden et al. (1996)
HLC	Henry's law constant	mol/(kg bar)		Hiatt (2013)

Bunsen coefficient (used in 16 publications)

		1		Cady and Misra (1974)
		1		Stock and Kuß (1917)
	absorption coefficient	1		Winkler (1891a)
	absorption coefficient	1		Winkler (1891b)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
	absorption coefficient	1		Winkler (1899)
	Bunsen partition coefficient	1		Smith et al. (1981b)
	solubility coefficient	1		Douglas (1967)
α	absorption coefficient	1		Bohr (1899)
α	Bunsen coefficient	1		Park et al. (1982)
α	Bunsen coefficient	1		Simpson and Lovell (1962)
α	solubility coefficient	1		Meadows and Spedding (1974)
α	solubility coefficient	1		Briner and Perrottet (1939)
β	absorption coefficient	1		Winkler (1901)
β	absorption coefficient	1		Winkler (1906)
β	Bunsen coefficient	1		Wisegarver and Cline (1985)
β	Bunsen solubility coefficient	1		Cline and Bates (1983)
amount fraction/pressure H_s^{xP} (used in 7 publications)				
		1/mmHg		Christie and Crisp (1967)
	Henry's law constant	1/atm		Lide and Frederikse (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	1/atm		Wilhelm et al. (1977)
H, H'	Henry's law coefficient	1/atm		De Bruyn et al. (1995b)
K	Henry's law constant	1/atm		Wen and Muccitelli (1979)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1/atm		Battino et al. (1983)
x		1/atm		Battino et al. (1984)
Henry's law volatility constants H_v (used in 388 publications)				
pressure/concentration H_v^c (used in 151 publications)				
		Pa m ³ /mol		MacBean (2012)
	Henry's constant	atm m ³ /mol		Staples et al. (1997)
	Henry's constant	mmHg/M		Glew and Moelwyn-Hughes (1953)
	Henry's law coefficient	Pa m ³ /mol		Schroeder and Munthe (1998)
	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Oliver (1985)
	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Smith et al. (1993)
	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Armbrust (2000)
	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		HSDB (2015)
	Henry's law constant	bar m ³ /mol		Lide and Frederikse (1995)
	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Friesen et al. (1993)
	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Siebers et al. (1994)
	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Siebers and Mattusch (1996)
	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Rubbiani (2013)
κ	Henry coefficient	bar L/mol		Braun and Dransfeld (1989)
κ'	Henry's law constant	atm/M		Templeton and King (1971)
H		atm/M		Jenkins and King (1965)
H		atm m ³ /mol		Woodrow et al. (1990)
H	Henry constant	atm m ³ /mol		Savary et al. (2014)
H	Henry constant	kPa m ³ /mol		Sieg et al. (2008)
H	Henry constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Watanabe (1993)
H	Henry's constant	atm m ³ /mol		Gossett et al. (1985)
H	Henry's constant	atm m ³ /mol		Webster et al. (1985)
H	Henry's constant	atm m ³ /mol		Gossett (1980)
H	Henry's constant	atm m ³ /mol		Lincoff and Gossett (1984)
H	Henry's constant	mmHg L/mol		Podoll et al. (1986)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
<i>H</i>	Henry's law coefficient	atm/M		Worthington and Wade (2007)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law coefficient	Pa m ³ /mol		Ballschmiter and Wittlinger (1991)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm/M		Dacey et al. (1984)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm cm ³ /mol		Kim et al. (2000)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm L/mol		Rinker and Sandall (2000)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Leuenberger et al. (1985)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Yaws et al. (1997)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Ashworth et al. (1988)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Cotham and Bidleman (1989)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Hawthorne et al. (1985)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Mackay and Yeun (1983)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Rathbun and Tai (1982)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Yaws (1999)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Metcalfe et al. (1980)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Slater and Spedding (1981)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Mackay and Leinonen (1975)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Arbuckle (1983)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Petrasek et al. (1983)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Warner et al. (1980)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Saçan et al. (2005)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Schroy et al. (1985)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Wolfe et al. (1980)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Mabury and Crosby (1996)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Shen (1982)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Yaws et al. (1998)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Opresko et al. (1998)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Mackay et al. (1979)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Nicholson et al. (1984)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Gossett (1987)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Robbins et al. (1993)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Yaws and Yang (1992)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Westcott et al. (1981)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Burkhard et al. (1985)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Yin and Hassett (1986)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Tse et al. (1992)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	kPa m ³ /mol		Govers and Krop (1998)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	kPa m ³ /mol		Hansen et al. (1993)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	MPa m ³ /mol		Zhang et al. (2013)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa L/mol		Schüürmann (2000)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Kurz and Ballschmiter (1999)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Sagebiel et al. (1992)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Paasivirta et al. (1999)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		ten Hulscher et al. (1992)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Kucklick et al. (1991)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Tremp et al. (1993)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Suntio et al. (1988)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Alaee et al. (1996)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Delgado and Alderete (2003)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Delgado and Alderete (2002)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Sahsuvar et al. (2003)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Shiu and Mackay (1986)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shiu and Ma (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shiu and Mackay (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Tittlemier et al. (2004)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Niinemets and Reichstein (2002)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Tittlemier et al. (2002)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Ferreira (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Li et al. (2003)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Fang et al. (2006)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (2006a)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (2006b)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (2006c)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (2006d)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Cetin et al. (2006)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Otto et al. (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Fang Lee (2007)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shen and Wania (2005)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Lei et al. (1999)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Riederer (1990)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Calamari et al. (1991)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Xiao et al. (2004)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		McPhedran et al. (2013)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Lee et al. (2012)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Bobra et al. (1985)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (1992)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (1993)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay et al. (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shiu et al. (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		De Maagd et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Drouillard et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shiu et al. (1994)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Hauff et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Fischer and Ballschmiter (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Jantunen and Bidleman (2006)
H, H'	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Bamford et al. (1999a)
H, H_c	Henry's law constant	$\text{atm m}^3/\text{mol}$		Chen et al. (2012)
H, K_{AW}	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Shunthirasingham et al. (2013)
H, K'_{AW}	Henry's law constant	$\text{kPa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Mackay and Shiu (1981)
H, k_{H}	Henry's law constant	$\text{atm m}^3/\text{mol}$		Heron et al. (1998)
H, H_c	Henry's constant	$\text{atm m}^3/\text{mol}$		Chang and Criddle (1995)
h_2	Henry's law constant	atm/M		Deno and Berkheimer (1960)
H_c	Henry's constant	$\text{atm m}^3/\text{mol}$		Kondoh and Nakajima (1997)
H_c	Henry's constant	mmHg/M		Smith et al. (1981a)
H_{W}	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Kuramochi et al. (2004)
H_{w}	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Kuramochi et al. (2014)
H_{pc}	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Copolovici and Niinemets (2005)
$H_{\text{pc}}, H_{\text{px}}, H_{\text{cc}}$	Henry's law constant	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Cimetiére and de Laat (2009)
K_{AW}^c	air-water partition coefficient	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Lei et al. (2007)
K_{AW}	air-water partition coefficient	$\text{Pa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Cousins and Mackay (2000)
K_{aw}	Henry's law constant	$\text{atm m}^3/\text{mol}$		Arp and Schmidt (2004)
K_{aw}, H_c	air/water partition coefficient	$\text{kPa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Ryu and Park (1999)
k_{H}	Henry constant	$\text{kPa m}^3/\text{mol}$		Haynes (2014)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
K_H	Henry's constant	atm cm ³ /mol		Zhang and Pawliszyn (1993)
K_h	Henry's law constant	atm/M		Kosak-Channing and Helz (1983)
K_H	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Perlinger et al. (1993)
K_H	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Wolfe et al. (1982)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Bamford et al. (2000)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Bamford et al. (2002)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Charles and Destailats (2005)
k_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Destailats and Charles (2002)
k_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Paasivirta and Sinkkonen (2009)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Lau et al. (2006)
k_H, H_{cc}	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Reza and Trejo (2004)
K_H, K_{AW}	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Wu and Chang (2011)
Hc	Henry's law constant	kPa m ³ /mol		Wang and Wong (2002)
He	Henry coefficient	atm cm ³ /mol		Joosten and Danckwerts (1972)
HLC	Henry's law constant	10 ⁻⁴ atm m ³ /mol		Dunnivant et al. (1988)
HLC	Henry's law constant	atm L/mol		Myrdal and Yalkowsky (1994)
HLC	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Dunnivant and Elzerman (1988)
HLC	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Sabljić and Güsten (1989)
HLC	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Dunnivant et al. (1992)
HLC	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Murphy et al. (1987)
HLC	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Bamford et al. (1999b)
HLC	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Santl et al. (1994)
HLC	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol		Krop et al. (1997)
HLC, K	Henry's law constant	atm m ³ /mol		Brunner et al. (1990)
concentration/concentration H_v^{cc} (used in 133 publications)				
		1		Feldhake and Stevens (1963)
	air-water partition coefficient	1		Atlas et al. (1983)
	air-water partition coefficient	1		Buttery et al. (1965)
	distribution coefficient	1		Wolfenden (1976)
	distribution coefficient	1		Bone et al. (1983)
	distribution constant	1		WHO (1990)
	Henry's constant	1		Marin et al. (1999)
	Henry's law coefficient	1		Schroeder and Munthe (1998)
	partition coefficient	1		Wolfenden and Williams (1983)
H	air-water partition coefficient	1		McLachlan et al. (1990)
H	distribution constant	1		Lindqvist and Rodhe (1985)
H	distribution ratio	1		Glotfelty et al. (1987)
H	Henry coefficient	1		Kanefke (2008)
H	Henry's constant	1		Ervin et al. (1980)
H	Henry's constant	1		Nirmalakhandan and Speece (1988)
H	Henry's constant	1		Jayasinghe et al. (1992)
H	Henry's constant	1		Anderson (1992)
H	Henry's constant	1		Hoyt (1982)
H	Henry's gas law constant	1		Pankow et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law coefficient	1		Dewulf et al. (1999)
H	Henry's law coefficient	1		Turner et al. (1996)
H	Henry's law coefficient	1		Johnson and Harrison (1986)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Moore (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Schoene and Steinhanses (1985)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Pfeifer et al. (2001)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
H	Henry's law constant	1		David et al. (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Harrison et al. (1993)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Sheikheldin et al. (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Yoshida et al. (1987)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Southworth (1979)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Eastcott et al. (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Yurteri et al. (1987)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Bierwagen and Keller (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Ji and Evans (2007)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Iverfeldt and Persson (1985)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Fischer et al. (2004)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Shimotori and Arnold (2003)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Lamarche and Droste (1989)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Balls (1980)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Görgényi et al. (2002)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Yoshida et al. (1983)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Plassmann et al. (2010)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Giardino et al. (1988)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Mazzoni et al. (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Liu et al. (2015)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Durham et al. (1981)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Dilling (1977)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Liss and Slater (1974)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Moore et al. (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Dewulf et al. (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Tancrede and Yanagisawa (1990)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Hunter-Smith et al. (1983)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Nirmalakhandan et al. (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Allen et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	1		Hilal et al. (2008)
H	partition coefficient	1		Atlas et al. (1982)
H	partition coefficient	1		Zafriou and McFarland (1980)
H, H'	Henry's law constant	1		Cetin and Odabasi (2005)
H'	Henry's law constant	1		Odabasi et al. (2006)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Breiter et al. (1998)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Munz and Roberts (1987)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Chai et al. (2005)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Garbarini and Lion (1985)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Gupta et al. (2000)
H_c	Henry's constant	1		Teja et al. (2001)
H_c	Henry's law constant	1		Peng and Wan (1998)
H_c	Henry's law constant	1		Vane and Giroux (2000)
H_C	Henry's law constant	1		Ayuttaya et al. (2001)
H_c	Henry's law constant	1		Kochetkov et al. (2001)
H_c, H'	Henry's law constant	1		Hamelink et al. (1996)
H_x, H_c	Henry's law constant	1		Munz and Roberts (1986)
H_x, H_y	partition coefficient	1		Dubik et al. (1987)
H_P	Henry's law constant	1		Ramachandran et al. (1996)
H_{cc}	Henry's law constant	1		Staudinger and Roberts (2001)
H_{px}, H_{cc}, H_{pc}	Henry's law constant	1		Staudinger and Roberts (1996)
K	air-water distribution ratio	1		Mirvish et al. (1976)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
K	air-water partition coefficient	1		Buttery et al. (1969)
K	air-water partition coefficient	1		Buttery et al. (1971)
K	distribution coefficient	1		Palmer et al. (1985)
k	Henry's constant	1		Nelson and Hoff (1968)
K	Henry's law constant	1		Elliott and Rowland (1993)
k	Henry's law constant	1		Fu et al. (2013)
K	partition coefficient	1		Dilling et al. (1975)
K	partition coefficient	1		Friant and Suffet (1979)
K'_H	Henry's constant	1		Bobadilla et al. (2003)
K'_H	Henry's law constant	1		Diaz et al. (2005)
K'_∞	Henry's law constant	1		Hwang et al. (1992)
$K_{WA}^c, K_{AW}^p, K_{AW}^x$	water-air partition coefficient	1		Lei et al. (2004)
K_i	distribution coefficient	1		Przyjazny et al. (1983)
$K_{air/water}$	air/water partition coefficient	1		Goss et al. (2006)
K_{AW}		1		Xiao et al. (2012)
K_{AW}	air-water partition coefficient	1		Amoore and Buttery (1978)
K_{aw}	air-water partition coefficient	1		Roberts and Pollien (1997)
K_{AW}	air-water partition coefficient	1		Li et al. (2007)
K_{aw}	air-water partition coefficient	1		de Wolf and Lieder (1998)
K_{aw}	air-water partition coefficient	1		Muir et al. (2004)
K_{AW}	air-water partition coefficient	1		Ma et al. (2010)
K_{AW}	air-water partition coefficient	Pa m ³ /J		Abou-Naccoul et al. (2014)
K_{AW}	air-water partition constant	1		Arp et al. (2006)
K_{AW}	air/water partition coefficient	1		Sarraute et al. (2004)
K_{AW}	air/water partition coefficient	1		Dohányosová et al. (2004)
K_{AW}	equilibrium partition coefficient	1		Zhang et al. (2010)
K_{AW}	Henry's law coefficient	1		Sieg et al. (2009)
K_{AW}	Henry's law constant	1		van Roon et al. (2005)
K_{aw}	partition coefficient	1		Wania and Dugani (2003)
K_{AW}	partition coefficient	1		Plassmann et al. (2011)
K_{AW}	partition coefficient	1		Xu and Kropscott (2014)
K_{AW}	partition coefficient	1		Xu and Kropscott (2012)
K_A	air-water partition coefficient	1		Kawamoto and Urano (1989)
K_D	distribution coefficient	1		Talmi and Mesmer (1975)
K_{GW}	gas-water partition coefficient	1		Fischer and Ballschmiter (1998)
K_{GW}	gas-water partition coefficient	1		Hauff et al. (1998)
K_{gw}	gas/water partition coefficient	1		Taft et al. (1985)
k_H	Henry's constant	1		Fernández-Prini et al. (2003)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1		Yates and Gan (1998)
k_H	Henry's law constant	1		Andersson et al. (2008)
k_H	Henry's law constant	1		Helburn et al. (2008)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1		Chesters et al. (1989)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1		Rice et al. (1997)
K_H	partition coefficient	1		Gan and Yates (1996)
k_v	partition coefficient	1		Chaintreau et al. (1995)
K_{WA}	water-air partition coefficient	1		Hoff et al. (1993)
p_c	partitioning coefficient	1		Cheng et al. (2003)
p_c	partitioning coefficient	1		Cheng et al. (2004)
S^*	dimensionless solubility	1		Elliott (1989)
Hc	Henry's coefficient	1		Bissonette et al. (1990)
Hc	Henry's constant	1		Chiang et al. (1998)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
Hc	Henry's constant	1		Ryan et al. (1988)
Hc	Henry's law constant	1		Wong and Wang (1997)
HLC	Henry's law constant	1		Fendinger and Glotfelty (1990)
HLC	Henry's law constant	1		Altschuh et al. (1999)
HLC	Henry's law constant	1		Fendinger and Glotfelty (1988)
HLC	Henry's law constant	1		Fendinger et al. (1989)
pressure/amount fraction H_v^{px} (used in 97 publications)				
		atm		Abraham (1984)
		atm		Abraham and Nasehzadeh (1981)
		atm		Abraham (1979)
		atm		Emel'yanenko et al. (2007)
		atm		Hertel and Sommer (2005)
		kPa		Dallos et al. (1983)
		kPa		Wright et al. (1992)
		mmHg		Signer et al. (1969)
		Pa		Fichan et al. (1999)
	Henry's constant	MPa		Lekvam and Bishnoi (1997)
	Henry's constant	Pa		Marin et al. (1999)
	Henry's law constant	mmHg/ppm		Sanders and Seiber (1983)
	Henry's law constant	mmHg		Ross and Hudson (1957)
<i>H</i>	Henry coefficient	atm		Hamm et al. (1984)
<i>H</i>	Henry coefficient	MPa		Reichl (1995)
<i>H</i>	Henry coefficient	MPa		Zheng et al. (1997)
<i>H</i>	Henry coefficient	MPa		Maaßen (1995)
<i>H</i>	Henry constant	kPa		Tabai et al. (1997)
<i>H</i>	Henry constant	mmHg		Rytting et al. (1978)
<i>H</i>	Henry fugacity	Pa		Rettich et al. (1992)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	atm		Conway et al. (1983)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	atm		Holzwarth et al. (1984)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	bar		Martikainen et al. (1987)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	GPa		Jou and Mather (2000)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	GPa		Carroll et al. (1997)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	GPa		Rettich et al. (1981)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Olson (1998)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Abd-El-Bary et al. (1986)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Falabella et al. (2006)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Falabella (2007)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Falabella and Teja (2008)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	kPa		Chapoy et al. (2004)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	MPa		Chapoy et al. (2005)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	MPa		Tsonopoulos and Wilson (1983)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	MPa		Heidman et al. (1985)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	MPa		Carroll and Mather (1989)
<i>H</i>	Henry's constant	MPa		Carroll et al. (1991)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law coefficient	bar		Warneck (1988)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	10 ² kPa		Mohebbi et al. (2012)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm		Yaws et al. (1997)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm		Riveros et al. (1998)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm		Roth and Sullivan (1981)
<i>H</i>	Henry's law constant	atm		Glew and Hames (1971)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
H	Henry's law constant	atm		Blatchley et al. (1992)
H	Henry's law constant	atm		Yaws et al. (1998)
H	Henry's law constant	atm		Yaws and Yang (1992)
H	Henry's law constant	GPa and bar		Bonifácio et al. (2001)
H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Zhu et al. (2000)
H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Dohnal and Fenclová (1995)
H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Straver and de Loos (2005)
H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Sotelo et al. (1989)
H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Nielsen et al. (1994)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa		Coquelet and Richon (2005)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa		Hovorka and Dohnal (1997)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa		Dohnal and Hovorka (1999)
H	Henry's law constant	Pa		Rettich et al. (1984)
H	Henry's law constant	Torr		Arijs and Brasseur (1986)
H'	Henry constant	bar		Severit (1997)
H_c	Henry's law constant	atm		Peng and Wan (1998)
H_c	Henry's law constant	MPa		Lau et al. (2010)
H_{12}	Henry's law constant	kPa		Beneš and Dohnal (1999)
K		atm		Ayers (1983)
K	distribution coefficient	atm		Leighton and Calo (1981)
k	Henry coefficient	atm		Sanemasa (1975)
k	Henry coefficient	atm		Benson et al. (1979)
K	Henry's constant	bar		Clever et al. (1985)
k	Henry's constant	Pa		Lodge and Danso (2007)
k	Henry's law constant	10^4 Pa		Khalfaoui and Newsham (1994b)
K	Henry's law constant	mmHg		Loomis (1928)
k	Henry's law constant	Torr		Keeley et al. (1988)
k^0	Henry's constant	bar		Crovetto (1991)
K^∞	limiting separation factor	atm		Hertel and Sommer (2006)
K^∞	limiting separation factor	atm		Hertel et al. (2007)
K^H	Henry's law constant	atm		Abraham and Matteoli (1988)
k_2	Henry constant	atm		Krause and Benson (1989)
K_H	Henry's constant	atm		Peng and Wan (1997)
k_H	Henry's constant	GPa		Fernández-Prini et al. (2003)
k_H	Henry's constant	GPa		Crovetto et al. (1982)
k_H	Henry's constant	MPa		Plyasunov (2012)
K_H	Henry's law coefficient	MPa		Iliuta and Larachi (2007)
K_H	Henry's law constant	10^7 Pa		Sanemasa et al. (1982)
K_H	Henry's law constant	10^7 Pa		Sanemasa et al. (1981)
K_H	Henry's law constant	atm		Green and Frank (1979)
k_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Bernauer et al. (2006)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Bernauer and Dohnal (2008)
k_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Bernauer and Dohnal (2009)
k_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Brockbank et al. (2013)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Dohnal et al. (2006)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Fenclová et al. (2014)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Torr		Tucker et al. (1981)
K_H, K_{AW}	Henry's law constant	MPa		Sarraute et al. (2006)
K_H	Henry's law constant	Pa		Sarraute et al. (2004)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa		Abou-Naccoul et al. (2014)
K_H	Henry's law constant	MPa		Dohányosová et al. (2004)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
p/N		mmHg		Butler and Ramchandani (1935)
p/N	distribution ratio	mmHg		Butler et al. (1935)
HLC	Henry's law constant	kPa		Xie et al. (2004)
pressure/molality H_v^{pb} (used in 7 publications)				
		atm kg/mol		Kelley and Tartar (1956)
		mmHg/(mmol/kg)		Saylor et al. (1938)
H	Henry's constant	atm kg/mol		Yoo et al. (1986)
H	Henry's constant	atm kg/mol		Edwards et al. (1978)
k_{aq}	Henry's law constant	atm kg/mol		Hill et al. (1968)
k_H	Henry's constant	kg kPa/mol		Ueberfeld et al. (2001)
K_H	Henry constant	bar kg/mol		Suleimenov and Krupp (1994)
Other (used in 38 publications)				
			ΔG and ΔH	Parsons et al. (1971)
			ΔG and ΔH	Parsons et al. (1972)
			$-\lg s$ and p_{sat}	Irmann (1965)
			aq. amount fraction and p in psia	Inga and McKetta (1961)
			aq. solution in % and p in mmHg	Klein (1982)
			special definition	Fishbein and Albro (1972)
			special definition	Berdnikov and Bazhin (1970)
		1	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{cc}	Cabani et al. (1981)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Cabani et al. (1975a)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Cabani et al. (1975b)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Cabani et al. (1978)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Andon et al. (1954)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Cabani et al. (1971a)
		atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Cabani et al. (1971b)
		atm	ΔG for H_v^{px}	Rochester and Symonds (1973)
		ml(gas)/ml(H2O)	special definition	Hempel (1901)
		ml(STDair)/liter(aq)	special definition	Carpenter (1966)
	absorption coefficient		similar to α	Rex (1906)
	Henry's law constant	atm	ΔG and ΔH for H_v^{px}	Arnett and Chawla (1979)
	solubility	mass%/atm	special definition	Booth and Jolley (1943)
α, A, l, q				Dean (1992)
λ	solubility coefficient		special definition	Kruis and May (1962)
H	Henry's constant		special definition	Chen et al. (1979)
H	Henry's constant	kPa/mass%	special definition	McLinden (1989)
H	Henry's law constant	dyne cm/g		Chiou et al. (1980)
H	Henry's law constant		special definition	Thompson and Zafiriou (1983)
H	solubility constant		special definition	St-Pierre et al. (2014)
H, K_{aw}, H_c	Henry's law constant		miscellaneous definitions	Park et al. (1997)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1/atm	product with acidity constant	Clegg et al. (1998)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1/atm	product with acidity constant	Clegg and Brimblecombe (1990)
K_H	Henry's law constant	1/atm	product with acidity constant	Carslaw et al. (1995)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol ² /(kg ² atm)	product with acidity constant	Clegg and Brimblecombe (1986)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol ² /(kg ² atm)	product with acidity constant	Brimblecombe and Clegg (1988)
K_H	Henry's law constant	mol ² /(kg ² atm)	product with acidity constant	Brimblecombe and Clegg (1989)
KS	solubility constant	M ² /atm	product with acidity constant	Chameides and Stelson (1992)
Q_i	modified Henry's law constant	M/atm		Weiss (1974)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
S	Kuenen coefficient	cm^3/g		Ashton et al. (1968)
s_0			special definition	Morrison and Johnstone (1954)
miscellaneous	miscellaneous	miscellaneous		Fogg and Sangster (2003)
Effective Henry's law constants				
H	effective Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Schwartz (1986)
H^*	effective Henry's law constant	M/atm		McNeill et al. (2012)
H^*	apparent Henry's law constant	M/atm		Seyfioglu and Odabasi (2007)
H^*	effective Henry's law constant	M/atm		Betterton (1991)
H^*	effective Henry's law constant	$\text{mol}/(\text{kg atm})$		Huthwelker et al. (1995)
H_{eff}	effective Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Volkamer et al. (2009)
H_{eff}	effective Henry's law constant	M/atm		Lelieveld and Crutzen (1991)
H_{eff}	effective solubility constant	M/atm		Chameides (1984)
K^*	apparent Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Zhou and Mopper (1990)
K_{H}	effective Henry's law coefficient	M/atm		Pandis and Seinfeld (1989)

Symbol	Name	Unit	Comment	Reference
Henry's law constants for non-aqueous solutions				
C	Henry's law constant	psia ⁻¹		Elbishlawi and Spencer (1951)
H	apparent Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Hajiw et al. (2017)
H	Henry's constant	kPa	f/x	Liu et al. (2017)
H	Henry's constant	MPa	f/x	Harifi-Mood (2020)
H	Henry's constant	MPa	f/x	He et al. (2017)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Linnemann et al. (2020)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Nikolaychuk et al. (2017)
H	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Song et al. (2019)
H_1	Henry's law constant	atm	p/w	Schotte (1982)
H_m, H_x	Henry's constant	MPa kg/mol, MPa	$f/b, f/x$	Li et al. (2016)
H_x	Henry's law constant	Pa m ³ /mol	p/c	Zhao et al. (2017)
H_{21}	Henry's constant	Atm	f/x	Lenoir et al. (1971)
H_{21}	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Jou et al. (2015)
H_g	Henry's law constant	kPa	?	Miyano et al. (2006)
$h_{H,x}^{(0)}$	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Shokouhi et al. (2019)
He	Henry's constant	kPa m ³ /kmol	p/c	Sema et al. (2019)
k	Henry's law constant	mm	p/x	Brown and Melchiorre (1965)
K_p	Henry's law constant	atm		Sugiyama et al. (1975)
K_A^H	limiting Henry's law constant	mm l/mol	p/c	Taha and Christian (1970)
k_H	Henry's constant	?	in Russian	Blank (1975)
k_H	Henry's constant	MPa	p/x	Safarov et al. (2018)
k_H	Henry's constant	MPa (per mol/kg)	f/b	Böttger et al. (2016)
K_H	Henry's law constant	atm	p/x	Goldman (1974)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa	p/x	Haidl and Dohnal (2017)
k_H	Henry's law constant	MPa	f/x	Minnick and Shiflett (2019)
k_H	Henry's law constant	MPa	p/x	Décultot et al. (2019)
$K_{H3,12}$	Henry's law constant	Pa	p/x	Mainar et al. (2019)
L_{21}, H_{21}	Ostwald coefficient, Henry fugacity	1, Pa	$c/c, p/x$	Hesse et al. (1999)
He	Henry's law constant	kPa m ³ /kmol		Ling et al. (2020)
He	miscellaneous	kPa m ³ /kmol		Liu et al. (2019)
Adsorption onto/into (semi-) solids				
D	solid-liquid partition coefficient	weight%/weight%	metal partitioning in iron meteorites	Chabot et al. (2003)
K	Henry's law constant	(molecules per cavity) / Torr	c/p (sorption in zeolites)	Ruthven and Derrah (1975)
k	Henry's law constant	mol g ⁻¹ Torr ⁻¹	amount absorbed in active carbon/ p	Boucher and Everett (1971)
K_H	Henry's law constant	kPa	in bitumen	Xu and Hepler (1990)
—	—	—	magma, garnet, olivine	Beattie (1993)

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